

Financial Performance Analysis of Selected Companies in Information Technology Sector

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Abstract: The Indian Information Technology (IT) Industry has always been a key part in growth of India. India has a flourishing IT industry, and earned a well-deserved place in the global market. Accounting for 7.4 percent of the GDP in the financial year 2022, the IT-BPM has played a significant role in India's socio-economic growth, so much so that it could be the future driver of modern India. The Indian government has been very supportive of the IT sector, providing various tax exemptions and financial benefits, which enabled India to become the home of many major IT companies, like Tata Consultancy Services, Infosys, Wipro, L&T Infotech, Mindtree, and Tech Mahindra. India's IT-BPM industry employed around 4.8 million personnel in financial year 2022. The IT spending of the country in 2022 was estimated to be around 101 billion U.S. dollars. But does this growth really turning into fortune for the IT companies or not. What are the adverse effects of this competitively growing sector on the fiscal well-being of the companies? In the context with current paper focuses on analysing the financial performance of three companies of IT sector for the duration of 10 years from 2012-13 to 2021-22. It analyses the fiscal well-being of selected units on the basis of selected variables depicting various parameters like leverage, liquidity and profitability of the concerned units. The paper also examines if the financial well-being of various selected companies is comparable or a significant difference exist in between them also.

Keywords: Financial performance , Information Technology, Leverage

Introduction

The Indian Information Technology (IT) Industry has always been a key part in growth of India. India has a flourishing IT industry, and earned a well-deserved place in the global market. Accounting for 7.4 percent of the GDP in the financial year 2022, the IT-BPM has played a significant role in India's socio-economic growth, so much so that it could be the future driver of modern India. The Indian government has been very supportive of the IT sector, providing various tax exemptions and financial benefits, which enabled India to become the home of many major IT companies, like Tata Consultancy Services, Infosys, Wipro, L&T Infotech, Mindtree, and Tech Mahindra. India's IT-BPM industry employed around 4.8 million personnel in financial year 2022. The IT spending of the country in 2022 was estimated to be around 101 billion U.S. dollars. India was the leading

outsourcing destination in the world, accounting for more than half of the market of the global information technology and business process management (IT & BPM) services in financial year 2021. The IT & BPM sector accounted for around 8% of India's GDP the same year. Rapid digitalization and transition to remote working helped the industry to stabilize its growth while facing the impact of the coronavirus pandemic. Anything involved with software, computers, networks, intranets, Web sites, servers, databases and telecommunications falls under the IT umbrella. IT is the technology that helps companies store, process and flow data within an organization. This sector ultimately serves other sectors like Banking, Manufacturing, Telecom, Hotels, Hospitals etc. to improve their efficiency and increase their revenues via customer satisfaction.

Source : <https://www.moneyworks4me.com/investmentshastra/it-sector-analysis-and-review-of-indian-economy/>

Top Players in the Indian IT Industry	
Segment	Top Players
IT-Software	Infosys, TCS, Wipro, HCL Tech
ITeS- BPO	Eclerx services, iSmart Global, 3i Infotech
IT-Hardware	HCL infosystem, Zenith Computers, Smartlink Networking
IT-Education	Aptech, NIIT, Educomp Solution

Current research focuses on analysing the financial performance of three companies of IT sector for the duration of 10 years from 2012-13 to 2021-22 ie Infosys, TCS and Wipro

Literature Review

N. Sathiyal and S. Sangeetha (2021) evaluated the financial performance as well as compare the performance of selected public sector and private sector banks in India for the five years period from 2014-15 to 2018-19. To compare the financial performance by using selected parameters namely return on asset, total income, net profit, net interest income and operating profit. As per the study, total income, net interest income and operating profit of selected public sector banks are performing better than private sector banks. On the other hand, net profit and return on assets of private sector bank is higher than public sector banks. There is no significant difference between the net profits of selected public sector and private sector banks. So, the private sector banks are more constant than public sector banks.

Dr. V. Devaki (2020) conducted the study to provide an overview of the capital structure of three private telecom service provider companies. Airtel, Vodafone and Tata Teleservices were considered for the study on the basis of some selection parameters. The study provides us an insight into the financing pattern, profitability, indebtedness and the components of capital structure of the selected telecom companies. The study focused on equity share capital parameter of the companies and the data was analysed using average mean statistical tool. The result depicted that the company capital structure is important for maintaining a good solvency position. This also confirms the theory that research and development activities will increase due to company capital structure Dr. Marimuthu, KN and Dr. Syed Azhar (2019) conducted the study to evaluate the fiscal strength of Indian telecommunication companies. The observation duration for the evaluation was from year 2013-14 to year 2017-18. The study was quantifiable and utilized Altman ‘Z’ score tool for recognizing the

fiscal stability of concerned companies. The data is secondary and was collected from yearly fiscal documents of the concerned companies for five year period under observation. The companies which were evaluated include Bharti Airtel, Vodafone Idea and RCOM. The statistical analysis was done using Dr. Edward I. Altman’s Multiple Discriminate Analysis on various financial ratios. The result of the study concluded that Bharti Airtel’s financial position was better and satisfactory as compared to that of Vodafone Idea and RCOM. Also, the entry of any such new service provider can completely disrupt the telecom industry.

P Jha (2018) conducted a study that reveals that the financial information facilitate the management in setting up plans and financial strategies.

Berna (Kiran) Bulgurcu (2012) in a study proposed a multi- criteria decision-making model to measure and compare the financial performance of thirteen technology firms trading in Istanbul Stock Exchange. These firms are examined and assessed in terms of ten financial ratios which are combined to obtain a financial performance score by using Technique for Order Preference by Similarity to Ideal Solution Methods (TOPSIS). This study found out that ranking results of Market Value are not comparable to the results of TOPSIS for technology firms in Turkey. TOPSIS method is not enough to evaluate the financial performances of technology firms in Turkey.

Dr S Usha (2010) performed a study for the selected 65 software companies and the summary statistics has been analysed to find out the overall financial performance. The results of the analysis show that some of the selected ratios have shown inconsistent performance in liquidity, solvency, efficiency, coverage, share related and profitability ratios. All the selected sample companies have been considered for the analysis i.e., Size wise classification has not been done before performing the ratio analysis and this may be one of the reason for the inconsistency of some of the ratios as size may be one of the factor that influences the financial performance. Another important reason for the

inconsistency may be the financial policies followed by the companies i.e. the selected companies have followed different financial policies.

Research Methodology

The present paper studies the IT Companies (TCS, Infosys and Wipro) on the basis of three diverse fiscal parameters leverage, liquidity and profitability of the selected companies.

Objective of the Study

- 1) Evaluating financial performance of chosen IT companies.
- 2) Correlating leverage position of chosen IT companies.

- 3) Correlating profitability performance of chosen IT companies.
- 4) Correlating liquidity of chosen IT companies.
- 5) Testing any significant difference is present in concerned variables or not.

Sample

Current paper studies the fiscal performance of three major players of IT sector of India. The companies are chosen on the basis of market capitalisation. The selected companies are Tata Consultancy Services (TCS), Infosys, Wipro.

List of Top 5 IT companies in India showing their market capitalization.

S.NO	COMPANY	MARKET CAPITALISATION (RS IN CRORES)
1	TCS	14,09,671
2	INFOSYS	7,12,779
3	WIPRO	3,48,343
4	HCL TECHNOLOGIES	3,46,114
5	TECH MAHINDRA	1,34,268

Source: <http://www.electronicandyou.com/blog/top-10-it-companies-in-india-by-market-cap.html>

Hypothesis

H₀₁: There is no significant difference in the profitability of chosen companies.

H₀₂ :There is no significant difference in the leverage of chosen companies.

H₀₃: There is no significant difference in the liquidity of chosen companies

Data Analysis & Interpretation

The fiscal performance of chosen IT companies is analyzed using various fiscal ratios. The statistical tools which have been used for data interpretation are averages (mean), standard deviation, minimum and maximum. The study is also conducted to evaluate whether the fiscal performance of chosen IT companies in terms of ratios is similar or have a significant difference. For testing the significant difference in financial performance ONE WAY ANOVA TEST is used. The analytical results are tested at 95% level of confidence (5% level of significance). When the evaluated value of F Ratio comes higher than the critical value at the 5% level of significance then the null hypothesis will be rejected and if the F Ratio value comes less than the

critical value corresponding null hypothesis will be accepted.

Limitations

The analysis is based on secondary data collected from various sources; therefore, the authenticity will be completely subjected to the available data. The sample size is also very limited. The time period considered for study is also limited to ten years.

DataAnalysis

Liquidity Ratio Analysis

A current ratio is a type of financial ratio used to determine a company's ability to pay its short-term debt obligations. It compares a firm's current assets to its current liabilities, and is expressed as follows

$$\text{Current ratio} = \frac{\text{Current Assets}}{\text{Current Liabilities}}$$

The current ratio is an indication of a firm's liquidity.

The metric helps determine if a company can use its current assets to cover its current liabilities. This analysis is of importance to all those interested in knowing the financial condition of the organization.

Table 1.1

Company	March 22	March 21	March 20	March 19	March 18	March 17	March 16	March 15	March 14	March 13
TCS	1.85	2.53	2.88	3.31	4.15	4.56	5.55	4.06	1.511	1.19
Infosys	1.99	2.545	2.61	2.83	3.54	3.83	3.90	4.14	4.71	5.61
Wipro	2.01	1.78	2.40	2.67	2.79	2.35	2.32	2.66	2.60	2.12

Source: <https://www.macrotrends.net/stocks>

If the current ratio is higher than the idle, then the company is in financially sound condition and can easily pay its liabilities and if the ratios are lower than it will not be a good idea to invest in that company. Idle current ratio is 2:1. Therefore from the above table

we can say currently Wipro is the only company with good current ratio and is capable of covering its current liabilities with current assets. Upto 2021 even TCS and Infosys were showing good current financial positions.

Table 1.2

Measure	TCS	Infosys	Wipro
Mean	3.16	3.57	2.37
Standard Deviation	1.425151	1.104	0.32444
High	5.55	5.61	2.79
Low	1.19	1.99	1.78

We can see from the above table that the average current ratio for all the selected companies had been significant over a period of 10 years. Wipro is showing least standard deviation in its current ratio and is not maintaining very high current ratio as well.

Quick Ratio Analysis

The quick ratio is an indicator of a company's short-term liquidity position and measures a company's ability to meet its short-term obligations with its most liquid assets. Since it indicates the company's ability to instantly use its near-cash assets (assets that can be converted quickly to cash) to pay down its current liabilities, it is also called the acid test ratio.

Table 1.3

Company	March 22	March 21	March 20	March 19	March 18	March 17	March 16	March 15	March 14	March 13
TCS	0.29	0.34	0.60	0.39	0.45	0.53	0.52	0.62	0.46	0.45
Infosys	2.10	2.74	2.88	3.0	3.78	4.05	3.98	3.12	3.83	4.82
Wipro	2.36	2.36	2.36	2.36	2.36	2.36	2.36	2.36	2.36	2.36

Source: <https://www.macrotrends.net/stocks>

If the quick ratio is higher than the idle, then the company is in financially sound short term liquidity position and if the ratios are lower than it will not be a good idea to invest in that company. Idle quick ratio is 1:1. Therefore from above table we can say

currently Wipro is the company with highest liquidity ratio and can therefore be considered with a good short term liquidity position. Even the short term liquidity position of Infosys is very good.

Table 1.4

Measure	TCS	Infosys	Wipro
Mean	0.47	3.43	2.36
Standard Deviation	0.10638	0.7979	0.2135
High	0.62	4.82	2.65
Low	0.29	2.10	2.01

We can see from the above table that the average quick ratio for all Infosys and Wipro is very good but that of TCS cannot be considered good as it is less than the idle ratio. TCS is showing least standard deviation in its quick ratio.

Leverage (Long-Term Solvency) Analysis

Long term solvency means the firm's ability to meet its liabilities in the long run. Long term solvency ratios help to determine the ability of the business to repay its debts in the long run. These ratios are used

to analyze whether the company will be able to get more finance in future or not.

Debt- Equity ratio Analysis

The debt-to-equity ratio, also referred to as debt-equity ratio (D/E ratio), is a metric used to evaluate a company's financial leverage by comparing total debt to total shareholder's equity. In other words, it measures how much debt and equity a company uses to finance its operations

Table 1.5

Company	March 22	March 21	March 20	March 19	March 18	March 17	March 16	March 15	March 14	March 13
TCS	0.37	0.46	1.17	0.96	1.12	1.41	1.53	1.62	1.66	2.71
Infosys	0.56	0.41	0.41	0.30	0.23	0.21	0.22	0.21	0.20	0.17
Wipro	0.09	0.01	0.01	0.05	0.09	0.04	0.04	0.03	0.03	0.00

Source: <https://www.macrotrends.net/stocks>

Debt-equity (D/E) ratio will depend on the nature of the business and its industry. Generally speaking, a D/E ratio below 1 would be seen as relatively safe, whereas values of 2 or higher might be considered risky. Therefore, from the above table we can say

currently Wipro is the company with lowest debt and is mainly financed through equity and can therefore be considered with a good long term solvency position since it has to pay least to the creditors in comparison to the other two selected

companies. But we can also see that other two companies are also working on Equity and less

dependent on debt which is an indication of good long term solvency position.

Table 1.6

Measure	TCS	Infosys	Wipro
Mean	1.30	0.29	0.04
Standard Deviation	0.668372	0.127174	0.031073
High	2.71	0.56	0.09
Low	0.37	0.17	0.00

We can see from the above table that the average debt equity ratio for Wipro is very low but that of TCS is very high comparatively. Wipro is maintaining a debt equity ratio as low as 0 with a standard deviation of just 0.03 which is a clear indication of very good long term solvency position of the company in comparison to other selected samples.

Profitability Analysis

To continue growing in an extremely dynamic, competitive, and vibrant market profitability

Table 1.7 (All figure as %)

Company	March 22	March 21	March 20	March 19	March 18	March 17	March 16	March 15	March 14	March 13
TCS	23.81	22.77	25.33	24.40	25.92	25.51	26.87	26.17	28.56	26.40
Infosys	20.43	21.00	19.66	20.11	26.08	23.30	23.51	25.71	22.99	24.79
Wipro	15.44	17.43	15.91	15.35	14.70	15.42	17.36	18.49	17.95	15.94

Source: <https://www.macrotrends.net/stocks>

From the above table we can say TCS is making highest net profit currently. Wipro is the company

analysis is a must. Profitability analysis helps businesses identify growth opportunities, fast/slow-moving stock items, market trends, etc, ultimately helping decision-makers see a more concrete picture of the company as a whole.

Net Profit Margin Analysis

The net profit margin is calculated as a percentage of net profit to sales. It is a metric used to evaluate a company's profitability which is required for long term sustenance in the market.

Net profit margin = (Net profit/ sales)*100

Table 1.8

Measure	TCS	Infosys	Wipro
Mean	25.57	22.76	16.40
Standard Deviation	1.638734	2.354942	1.294402
High	28.56	26.08	18.49
Low	22.77	19.66	14.70

We can see from the above table that selected companies have been able to maintain high net profit over the years. The average net profit margin of Wipro is the least in comparison to TCS and Infosys. To continue growing in an extremely dynamic, competitive, and vibrant market WIPRO can identify new growth opportunities to make more profits.

Dividend Per Share Analysis

Dividend per share (DPS) is the sum of declared Dividend Per Share (DPS) = (D - SD)/S

Where

D = sum of dividend over a period

SD = Special Dividends

S= number of outstanding shares

Table 1.9 (All figures in RS)

Company	March 22	March 21	March 20	March 19	March 18	March 17	March 16	March 15	March 14	March 13
TCS	43.00	38.00	73.00	30.00	50.00	47.00	43.50	79.00	32.00	22.00
Infosys	31.00	27.00	17.50	21.50	43.50	5.75	24.25	59.50	63.00	42.00
Wipro	6.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	2.00	6.00	12.00	8.00	7.00

Source: <https://www.macrotrends.net/stocks>

with least profit margins. But all the 3 selected companies are making profit over the years.

dividends issued by a company for every ordinary share outstanding. The figure is calculated by dividing the total dividends paid out by a business, including interim dividends, over a period of time, usually a year, by the number of outstanding ordinary shares issued. The net profit margin is calculated as a percentage of net profit to sales. It is a metric used to evaluate a company's profitability which is required for long term sustenance in the market.

From the above table we can say TCS has highest dividend per outstanding share currently. Wipro is the company with least current DPS.

Table 1.10

Measure	TCS	Infosys	Wipro
Mean	45.75	33.50	4.50
Standard Deviation	18.07892	18.32613	3.865805
High	79.00	63.00	12.00
Low	22.00	5.75	1.00

We can see from the above table that selected 2 companies ie TCS and Infosys have been able to maintain high DPS. The average DPS of Infosys and TCS is very high whereas that of Wipro is

comparatively low. The lowest DPS is seen in Wipro which is as low as Rs 1.00 whereas the lowest DPS of TCS is RS 22.00 and going as high as RS 45.75 over the years.

Hypothesis Testing

Table 1.11: Results of one way ANOVA test

ANALYSIS	F value (At 95% level of significance)
LIQUIDITY RATIO	
Current Ratio	3.31864
Quick Ratio	104.3788
LEVERAGE (LONG-TERM SOLVENCY)	
Debt – Equity Ratio	28.83126
PROFITABILITY RATIO	
Net profit margin	66.898
Dividend per share	19.8677

The critical value of F-Ratio at 95% level of significance is 2.866. For liquidity, Leverage and Profitability, all chosen variables has F ratio value higher as compared to critical value, therefore null hypothesis will be rejected for all these and a conclusion can be given that there is a significant difference in the fiscal performance of chosen companies in terms of Liquidity, Leverage and profitability.

Conclusion

The current study on chosen IT companies which is done for a duration of ten years (from 2012-13 to 2021-22) reveals that there is significant difference in the financial performance of the companies. Wipro has performed well across all financial variables except for profitability. The company has performed exceptionally well in short term liquidity and leverage as compared to the other two selected companies. Infosys has been able to maintain a decent quick ratio in comparison to TCS therefore, is in a better position to repay debts. Wipro has good leverage ratio and is working more on equity to give a strong long term solvency position to the company. In terms of Profitability variables, TCS and Infosys have performed extremely well signifying that they were able to generate profit over the years. Comparatively Wipro is not doing as good as the other two samples.

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